

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Department for Transport

Understanding behaviour of
transport users

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

The Department for Transport (DfT) supports the transport network that facilitates the movement of businesses, people, and goods across the UK. DfT plans and invests in transport infrastructure to ensure the country stays on the move.

As part of its data-driven approach to transport decision-making, this project aims to gain a deeper understanding of transport users' behaviour to enhance transport services. The primary objective is to analyse available datasets to understand transport users' behaviour, the challenges they face while travelling, and the factors that influence their decisions. Insights derived from the analysis of diverse data sources are intended to improve transport services and inform policy-making.

1.2 Data overview

DfT has provided access to various datasets for the challenge, including:

1. National Travel Survey (NTS) 2019 (England only): This survey collects information on how, why, when, and where people travel, as well as factors that affect travel, such as car availability and driving license holding. Approximately 16,000 individuals in 7,000 households in England participate in the survey each year.
2. Mobile phone data 1: This dataset captures trips from mobile phone devices from March 2019 to February 2020. It includes information on the origin and destination of trips, as well as the time of day.
3. Mobile phone data 2: This dataset represents a limited part of the UK but provides more detailed information, including individual trips made by specific individuals, the mode of transport used, and the start and end times. It also includes a unique ID for each individual, allowing for the identification of multi-stage trips.
4. Connectivity scores (England and Wales only): This dataset consists of connectivity scores by mode and trip purpose for each Lower Layer Super Authority Area (LSOA) in England and Wales, as well as origin-destination pairs journey times data.

5. Census data (England & Wales): This dataset provides information on population and households, but it was not used by our group for this challenge.

1.3 Main objectives

The main objectives of this challenge are to understand transport users' behaviour and identify areas for improvement. To achieve this, the challenge has been divided into three research questions:

- **How are passengers' journeys distributed geographically and what patterns exist?** This question aims to understand individual trip journeys, looking at the sequence and average duration. We also looked at the wait times, and geographical distribution with the aim of understanding individual journey patterns and potential pain points. To address these questions we have used the NTS and Connectivity scores datasets.
- **What individual journey patterns can be observed using Mobile Phone data?** This question seeks to understand how transport usage varies between geographical regions and over time. We used NTS, connectivity and Mobile Phone data sets to address this question.
- **What can be inferred about individual attitudes towards travelling using the NTS datasets?** This question investigates individual attitudes about travelling over time for different groups and external factors that influence travel attitudes.

1.4 Approach

To analyse the data, we utilised descriptive and statistical tools to identify key characteristics and trends. Descriptive statistics were applied to examine the geographical distributions of modes of travel, stratified by categories such as age, income bands, and working status. Additionally, descriptive statistics were employed to visualise the distributions of trip duration, number of journeys, waiting times, and the number of people travelling within a 24-hour period.

Spatial autocorrelation and Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA) were used to identify clusters of regions with varying connectivity scores and to understand their relationships with neighbouring regions. The team also cleaned and linked various datasets, including linking National Travel Survey (NTS) data

with connectivity scores data. Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) and correlation matrices were employed to extract insights from connectivity scores and satisfaction rates. Finally, linear regression models were used to statistically assess the impact of different variables on waiting times and to model travel growth.

1.5 Main conclusions

The main conclusions drawn from the analysis are as follows:

The car is the dominant mode of transportation across all age groups and regions, except in London, where travel patterns differ significantly. In the capital, higher-income groups are more likely to use the underground, while lower-income groups rely on other modes of transport. Similarly, in nearby regions such as the East of England and the South East, individuals in higher-income bands show a stronger preference for surface rail services, reflecting the influence of income and proximity to London on transport choices.

Connectivity varies significantly between regions, shaping travel satisfaction and accessibility. Large cities generally enjoy high connectivity, but their neighboring areas often have much lower scores. In contrast, rural areas and their surrounding regions consistently report low connectivity. This disparity is further reflected in public transport satisfaction, which is closely linked to connectivity. Interestingly, satisfaction with walking and cycling declines as connectivity improves, a trend likely influenced by external factors such as weather conditions, environmental quality, and perceived safety.

Age also plays a key role in travel behaviors, with younger individuals, especially those under 45, accounting for most trips. Cycling is primarily used for commuting, while walking and driving dominate overall travel patterns. On average, people make two journeys—or four trips—per day, highlighting the centrality of personal transportation. However, waiting times between trips are noticeably longer during off-peak hours, reflecting reduced service availability during these times.

Travel patterns across a 24-hour period reveal further complexities. The proportion of people traveling fluctuates non-linearly throughout the day, underscoring how factors like time, connectivity, and transport availability interact to influence behavior. These insights highlight the intricate relationship between transport options, regional characteristics, and individual choices.

1.6 Limitations

Some of our analyses were limited due to issues with merging different datasets, such as changes in the definitions of geographical areas over different time frames. Additionally, missing data prevented some investigations into potential interactions between variables.

The lack of standardisation for categories of geographical regions also hindered some analyses. For example, the definition of ‘county’ seems to change over shorter time periods: there may have been a significant renaming of local government areas that is not traced in all data sets; some counties are listed as a unitary authorities (UA) while others are split into more than one UA.

The mobile phone data only included people who could download the specific app on their mobile phones. This implies that the data may not be representative of the population. Furthermore, half of the postcodes in the data included less than 20 app users and the attrition rate of the app users was high (53%). Because of these factors we caution against overinterpreting the results.

1.7 Recommendations and future work

The following recommendations are provided:

- Further merging of datasets, such as Individual and Household datasets with Trip and Stage datasets, could provide valuable insights into the geographical distributions of single and multi-stage trips.
- Standardised categories for geographical areas would improve analyses over different time frames.
- Connectivity scores should consider other external factors, such as weather, environment, and sense of safety, to better understand their relationship with other datasets.
- Improvements to the quality of mobile phone data could be made by addressing issues such as phone battery drain, accuracy of app tracking for mode of transport categorisation, and recording of start and end times.

2 Geographical Journey Analysis

In this section, we aim to understand individual trip journeys by examining the sequence and average duration. We explore wait times and geographical distribution in order to identify individual journey patterns and potential pain points.

2.1 Dataset Description - Household and Individual data (NTS)

The National Travel Survey (NTS) data is collected exclusively from England and focuses on the year 2019. It comprises five datasets: 'Household', 'Individual', 'Trip', 'Stage', and 'Attitudes'.

The 'Household' dataset contains 6789 unique Household ID numbers, representing 6789 distinct households. The 'Individual' dataset also includes the same 6789 unique 'HouseholdID', but it consists of 15953 observations (rows). Initially, socio-demographic and transport users' information from the 'Household' and 'Individual' datasets were extracted.

From the 'Household' dataset, the following variables were extracted: household ID, Age/Sex, number of people living in the household, number of household vehicles, number of cars, bikes, bicycles, motorcycles, etc., household's income band, and region of the household.

The second dataset contains individual information, providing additional socio-demographic and other transport-related details. The following variables were extracted from this dataset: household ID, age, sex, socio-economic group, working status of the individual (including data about employment status such as full-time/part-time, self-employed, retired, student, disabled, and others), usual means of travel to work, and county name.

The main objective of utilising these datasets was to identify the geographical distribution of key factors and characteristics influencing the choice of transport mode for the population residing in those areas. Therefore, we decided to merge the 'Household' and 'Individual' datasets using the key Household ID. Subsequently, we aggregated information from the 'Individual' dataset for each region. The result was a dataset containing social, economic, and demographic features for each of the nine regions in England.

Figure 1: Geographical distribution of mode of travel to work by age categories

2.2 Approach and Findings

Figure 1 shows descriptive graphs of geographical distribution of mode of travel to work by age categories (< 16, 17 – 39, 40 – 59, > 60 years), income bands (< 25, 000, 25, 000 – 49, 999, > 50, 000) and working status (full-time, part-time, retired/permanently sick, other non-work).

Figure 1 shows the distribution of usage of different transportation types by age categories for 9 regions of England. We find that across age groups and all regions (except London), car is the main transport type used to commute to work. In London, a higher proportion of working aged population (17-39 years) used public transport than private cars. Among public transport, underground was more popular than buses and other transportation types.

According to Figure 2, for every income band group in all regions, private car was the main mode of transportation used to commute to work. This was different for London. In London, population in higher income band used underground services more often compared to those in lower income bands. Those in lower income bands are more likely to use the bus than the underground. In addition, from Figure 2 we can also see that households with the highest income bands in East of England and South East regions, which are close to London, used surface

Figure 2: Geographical distribution of mode of travel to work by income bands

rail services more often compared to other regions and other public transportation types.

Figure 3 shows that, overall, people who work full-time had a higher number of trips. For full-time workers in all regions except London, car was the main transportation type used to travel to work. In London, public transportation took higher share than private ones. Again, underground, bus and surface rail services were more popular for this population group, as well as for part-time workers. In other regions, walk, surface rail and bus services were less popular mode of transportation. In all other regions for part-time and non-working populations, car remained the main choice of transportation type to commute to work.

2.2.1 Future Recommendations

- To link this merged (Individual and Household) dataset to the 'Trip' and 'Stage' datasets, to analyse the geographical distribution of single and multi-stage trips, as well as the number of stages. This analysis, stratified by public transportation type, could enable the identification of geographical areas with higher pain points.
- We aimed to investigate the difficulties populations face in accessing public

Figure 3: Geographical distribution of mode of travel to work by working status

transport, but due to missing data in those variables, we were not able to achieve this objective. Completeness of these variables would allow us to connect information about the geographical distribution of the mode of transportation used to commute to different places, as well as to identify problems in access which could help solve these issues.

- The same approach could be used to look at stratified distribution by age groups. For example, issues in accessing public transport for the population commuting to schools and universities could be studied in each region.
- Lastly, information about the Index of Multiple Deprivation of Households/Regions could be used to identify the effect of economic status on other transport user behaviour characteristics.

2.3 Exploratory spatial analysis

Spatial data such as connectivity scores across England and Wales are spatially autocorrelated: we expect areas near each other to be more similar in terms of connectivity scores than areas that are farther apart. To represent spatial autocorrelation of connectivity scores, we used Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA). With LISA, we can find clusters of spatial autocorrelation

across different areas. Figures 4-8 show clusters of connectivity scores for different modes of transport. *HH* regions have high connectivity scores and have neighbours that also have high connectivity scores. *HL* regions have high connectivity scores and have neighbours that have low connectivity scores. *LH* regions have low connectivity scores and have neighbours that have high connectivity scores. *LL* regions have low connectivity scores and have neighbours that also have low connectivity scores. *HH* and *LL* areas contribute significantly to a positive global spatial autocorrelation, whereas *HL* and *LH* areas contribute significantly to a negative spatial autocorrelation. Other areas are not significantly contributing to the global autocorrelation.

We find that regions with large cities are highly connected but have neighbouring areas that have low connectivity scores. More rural areas have low connectivity scores and have neighbouring regions that have lower connectivity scores as well. We also find that the LISA cluster map for car as a mode of transport (Figure 5) is different compared to the LISA cluster maps for other modes of transportation (see Figures 6, 7, and 8). *HH* and *ns* regions are more prevalent with car as a mode of transport compared to other modes.

2.4 Linking Trip & Stage to Connectivity Data

2.4.1 National Travel Survey (NTS)

The NTS data includes household surveys that monitor trends in personal travel. The NTS provides up-to-date and regular information about personal travel within England and monitors trends in travel behaviour. It includes five different subsets encompassing the following components:

- Attitudes
- Stage
- Household
- Individual
- Trips

The different variables it uses to capture the aforementioned information are found on the website for UK Data Archive Data Dictionary [1].

The segregation of some of the key variables in the entire dataset is listed in Figure

LISA Cluster Map for connectivity score of overall

Figure 4: LISA cluster map of connectivity score of overall travel mode. HH: high-high; HL: high-low; LH: low-high; LL: low-low; ns: not significant.

LISA Cluster Map for connectivity score of overall_car

Figure 5: LISA cluster map of connectivity score of cars. HH: high-high; HL: high-low; LH: low-high; LL: low-low; ns: not significant.

LISA Cluster Map for connectivity score of overall_cycling

Figure 6: LISA cluster map of connectivity score of cycling. *HH*: high-high; *HL*: high-low; *LH*: low-high; *LL*: low-low; *ns*: not significant.

LISA Cluster Map for connectivity score of overall_walk

Figure 7: LISA cluster map of connectivity score of walking. *HH*: high-high; *HL*: high-low; *LH*: low-high; *LL*: low-low; *ns*: not significant.

LISA Cluster Map for connectivity score of overall_pt

Figure 8: LISA cluster map of connectivity score of public transportation. *HH*: high-high; *HL*: high-low; *LH*: low-high; *LL*: low-low; *ns*: not significant.

9, which could be found in the National Travel Survey Data Extract User Guide, 1995-2016 [2].

Levels in the NTS database

Figure 9: Levels in the NTS dataset

Only the Stage and Trips component data were used for linkage with other data sets below. The stage modes are just different ways to aggregate the same data, and they come in numerous versions. When there is a trip with multiple stages, only one mode can be counted as the main mode, and it is usually the stage with the longest distance. If there is more than one stage with the same distance, the latest one would be the main mode.

2.4.2 Connectivity Scores EW (England & Wales)

Connectivity data measures how connected people are to the places they want to go. It measures the opportunity to travel to various destinations, weighted by people’s overall proclivity to take those options. It aims to capture as many methods of travel, destination types, and people’s preferences as possible.

2.4.3 External Datasets used

In addition to the dataset provided, the following datasets were also used:

1. **UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) Regions and associated local authorities (LAs) in England** [3]:

This document contains all the UKHSA regions and associated local authorities (LAs) in England, published in October 2022.

2. **National Statistics Postcode Lookup UK [4]:**

This dataset contains the National Statistics Postcode Lookup (NSPL) for the United Kingdom. The NSPL relates current postcodes to a range of current statutory administrative, electoral, health, and other statistical geographies via ‘best-fit’ allocation from the 2011 Census output areas. It supports the production of area-based statistics from postcoded data. This was published in August 2021.

3. **Lower layer Super Output Area population estimates (supporting information) [5]:**

This dataset contains mid-year (30 June) estimates of the usual resident population for Lower layer Super Output Areas (LSOAs) in England and Wales by single year of age and sex, published in September 2021.

Each of them was used with distinctive purposes to properly link the combined trip and stage data of the NTS to the survey data. Their purposes will be explained in the later section.

2.4.4 Initial Analysis

The stage data within the NTS dataset explores the different modes of transportation used by a household in a trip/journey. A journey can have more than one mode of transportation. Analysing these datasets gives us different insights about the data, which was used in the initial stages to choose the variables that were useful for the later analysis and linkage of the different datasets.

Stage Time vs Stage Distance Figure 10 shows a heatmap of the time and distance for each stage. While the correlation between them is evident, a few of the stage times seem to be much more compared to the distance covered. This could possibly be dependent on the mode of stage and/or transport; or because of other external factors.

Short walk trips only The data in general, had significant number of short walks, both within the counties and in different counties. As can be seen from Figure 11, while understandably the majority of the count is for journeys within the same county, a few short walks are also there across different counties. The

Stage Time	Stage Distance	1 to under 2 miles	10 to under 15 miles	100 to under 150 miles	15 to under 25 miles	150 to under 200 miles	2 to under 3 miles	200 miles +	25 to under 35 miles	3 to under 5 miles	35 to under 50 miles	5 to under 10 miles	50 to under 75 miles	75 to under 100 miles	Under 1 mile
1 under 1.5 hours		200	893	29	1261	0	349	12	1253	505	1686	836	893	116	0
1.5 under 2 hours		20	121	101	151	13	31	4	132	84	303	134	781	419	0
15 under 30 mins		13803	7044	0	1769	0	8419	0	75	18390	18	24544	1	0	3330
2 under 2.5 hours		10	14	334	38	16	1	21	41	40	72	44	263	335	0
2.5 under 3 hours		0	2	266	3	50	2	22	10	7	5	14	53	99	0
3 under 4 hours		2	4	237	5	187	0	63	6	2	11	10	29	40	0
3 under 8 mins		15527	0	0	0	0	4937	0	0	1636	0	138	0	0	11188
30 under 45 mins		6435	6917	0	6497	0	1714	1	1133	3533	217	8307	9	0	247
4 under 5 hours		0	2	39	0	71	1	93	0	0	1	6	6	5	0
45 mins under 1 hour		595	1451	0	2550	0	825	1	1827	652	780	1425	81	7	18
5 under 6 hours		0	6	4	0	38	0	80	0	1	0	2	2	0	0
6 hours +		0	1	6	0	17	0	67	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8 under 15 mins		12272	145	0	4	0	13075	0	0	12259	0	3795	0	0	5765
Less than 3 mins		408	0	0	0	0	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1989

Figure 10: Stage distance in miles (x-axis, shown on top) and time (y-axis). The heatmaps shows the number of trips for each stage distance and time pair.

reason could be because both of those counties are in close proximity and within walking distance.

Observation for journeys While short walks also form a part of journeys, they were assumed to not have much importance while analysing the connectivity of that place, since those would not be impacted by how well-connected that place is. Analysis of how frequent the journeys are across the counties is shown in Figure 12. This figure indicates that London is the most commuted area across all its counties, with the top 10 most frequent journeys being seen across the different counties within and adjoining it. This clearly indicates why the connectivity scores are essential to further analyse if that could be a reason for the frequency of journeys in those regions which are well-connected than those which are not.

These points lead up to the necessity of linking the two provided datasets: NTS and connectivity scores EW, to further explore different modes and purposes of

Figure 11: Short walks within the same county or across different counties (note different scales for y-axis for each figure.)

Figure 12: Most frequently commuted counties.

transportation across England.

2.4.5 Methodology

The steps that are followed are listed as follows:

Figure 13: Flowchart of the steps to this linkage

Figure 13 corresponds to the following steps.

Before Step 1 we need to take the following actions. Understanding & Cleaning the datasets. The first task was to read the general description of all the primary data in question from the documentation described in Section 2.4.1 and shortlist the variables of interest. The variables were selected based on the objective. While some of the variables were more useful for performing analysis, the primary goal of this section was to link the data. After researching the variables, both similar and different in each of them, **three** factors were selected as variables to map the three datasets, namely county, purpose, and mode of transport. Some key changes were made to all three datasets before performing the mapping and linkage.

Choosing the variables in data. In the trip data, the variables only focusing on the trip origins and destinations were used, including the time duration, purposes (to and from both), and their geographical locations at the county, area type, and unitary authority levels. After further research, it was decided to take the county as the geographical measurement for this experimentation since the county councils are seen to be responsible for functions such as transport. Similarly, for the stage data, the distance and time were of primary focus apart from the ID keys.

Changing the categories. Since the categories in the county variable were numerical, it was changed to their labels as per the data dictionary, for the ease of performing mapping while linking.

Step 1. Combining the trip and stage datasets. The primary key taken to join these datasets are HouseholdID and TripID. The StageID was omitted since there could be more than one stage present in a journey for each trip. For this stage, the focus was only taken on the main mode of the journey (i.e., the longest journey), which was present in the trip data. For analysis purposes, it was initially noted which were the most frequent stage numbers for each journey, to give an idea of how many modes an individual usually has to take for each journey.

Step 2. Adding various external datasets to properly structure and enrich the data to move onto the next step. The different datasets and their purpose of usage are listed below:

- a) First the population for each LSOA provided in the external data on population 3 is joined to the connectivity data. The connectivity is then calculated for the purposes and modes with respect to the population in their respective LSOA (see Figure 45 in Appendix).

Note: The rationale for including the population is to consider the fact that the population is not equally distributed across all the LSOAs as some might be more densely populated than others. This could also impact the connectivity score in those regions. Hence taking a weighted average with respect to population is essential.

- b) Using the external data on National Statistics (see Section 2), the LSOA are mapped to their respective counties in the connectivity data.
- c) Taking the mean across every county with grouped LSOAs (see Figure 46 in Appendix).
- d) Mapping the connectivity scores of all the variables to each county in the dataset.

Step 3. This step mainly focuses on modifying the data variables from both datasets in order to join them based on:

- Counties

- Purpose of travel
- Mode of travel

Keeping in mind that the NTS data focuses on England only in 2019, and the connectivity data is relatively new and focuses on both England and Wales, the counties which existed outside of England were removed from the connectivity data before linking it with the NTS.

Before standardization, similar to the counties, the numerical categorical values of main modes and purposes of transport in the combined trip and stage dataset needed to be changed to their corresponding labels as per the data dictionary.

Each trip had a variable for three kinds of purposes under it:

- Trip purposes to
- Trip purpose from
- Trip purpose

Considering that only the whole purpose of the trip was of interest, the variable ‘Trip purpose’ was only used. Additionally, there were even more divergence within this variable in the form of:

- *TripPurpose_B01ID*: Trip purpose - full list - 23 categories
- *TripPurpose_B02ID*: Trip purpose - publication table breakdown - band A - 14 categories
- *TripPurpose_B04ID*: Trip purpose - publication table breakdown - band C - 8 categories

But only the variable with the full list of all 23 categories were taken.

To standardise using the purpose and mode of transport, both of these variables in the NTS combined data were joined as a single variable to match with the variables in the connectivity data. The connectivity data had their variables in the form of joined ‘purpose_mode’, with a score attached to it, based on each county (after Step 2). For example, a county would have each column dedicated for a purpose and mode of transport depicting its respective score on a scale of 1-100 (a score of 100 indicates a very well-connected place).

The following Table 2 shows how the variables in NTS data were condensed from 23 values of purposes and 13 values of modes to their respective condensed

forms.

These were then joined together to form a new variable named *purpose_mode* in the NTS dataset. Consequently, this was used to join the datasets by introducing the information from the connectivity dataset and mapping them as a set of new variables for both the origin and the destination counties of the trips (see Figure 47 in Appendix).

The data is now ready to be analysed further to develop inferences. The entire code can be found in this github file [6].

2.4.6 Issues and assumptions

Granularity of geographical location used To avoid any direct or indirect identifiers to the individuals while experimentation, it was decided not to choose the lowest level of geographic hierarchy, i.e., LSOA or even MSOA; and not too broad like Region. Hence, county was decided as the geographical indicator for this analysis.

Non-standardised county names This issue came up partly because of the unavailability of any (external or internal) dataset which could provide the same number and names of the counties as was provided in the combined NTS data. This could be because of various reasons, such as:

- Re-labelling of the local government areas, resulting in change of boundaries over different years.
- Some of the counties are listed in the unitary authorities (UA), while other counties are split into more than one UA.
- Joining datasets from multiple sources with different categories for the same geographical quantity.

This severely restricted further analysis of the linked data, as much of the data could not be matched due to differences in categories. For this experiment, after investigating a few different open-sourced datasets, we decided not to manually change the names to match the counties in both datasets due to time limitations. This drawback limited further experimentation after linking the data.

Different categories of modes of transport and purposes While the connectivity data had sparse variety of variables with different combinations of

Before	After
Walk	walk
Bicycle Motorcycle	cycling
Car/van driver Car/van passenger Other private transport	car
Bus in London Surface Rail London Underground Taxi/minicab Non-local bus Other local bus Other public transport	pt

Table 1: Modes

Before	After
Personal business medical, Personal business other, Commuting, Escort commuting, Escort business & other work, Personal business eat/drink, Other non-escort, Other work	Business
Education, Escort education, Entertain/public activity	Education
Food shopping, Non food shopping, Escort shopping /personal business	Shopping
Eat/drink with friends, Escort home (not own) & other escort	Visit friends at private homes
Day trip, Just walk, Sport: participate, Other social, Holiday: base	Entertainment public activity

Table 2: Purposes

modes (walk, cycling, car and public transport) with five unique purposes; the NTS data had a lot more. This fine-grained detailing is essential for better analysis, but not so much for linkages. The grouping of the condensed variables for this experiment is assumed to be the best representation while moving forward with the data.

Chronological and geographical discrepancy around the datasets The NTS survey dataset was published in 2019, and collected information on households in England only; while connectivity data is relatively new and provides contextual information on connectivity around both England and Wales. Since the administrative areas could change within a given time frame, it is assumed to be the same in this dataset.

2.4.7 Recommendations

- Use datasets collected around the same time frame for linking between them and developing useful insights from multiple sources.
- To align the different modes and purposes to a standard one, a general consensus should be reached across the various datasets to maintain consistency of the information, in order to avoid misrepresentation and loss of data. Knowledge of **domain experts** is highly recommended to maintain consistency of the terms.
- As a solution to non-standardised geographical locations at the county level, a more detailed approach may be useful. That is, analysing at LSOA or MSOA level, which appeared to be more consistent throughout all sources of data.

3 Connectivity scores England and Wales and NTS attitude: DAG analysis

Causal knowledge involves awareness and understanding of real-world cause-and-effect relationships to predict the outcome of an action and the mechanism of transition from one state to another through different interventions. This challenge primarily focuses on improving user experience. Therefore, understanding causal dependencies will play an important role in testing the outcomes of different

scenarios to enhance strategic decisions, such as how to improve user satisfaction using connectivity scores. To accomplish this, an algorithm for learning directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) is utilized, along with a correlation heat map.

3.1 DAG learning from connectivity scores and satisfaction rates

Two data sets were merged using the LSOA feature, which is a location indication. The satisfaction rates were categorized by calculating the mean for each region. For the Connectivity data set, only overall scores by mode and reason were considered. For the NTS attitude dataset, the average mean scores by region and mode were taken into account.

When merging the data sets, the extra rows were deleted, and 30,415 samples were retained to train the model. Table 3 displays the dependency scores learned from the merged data set (a threshold of 0.8 was set to retain strong dependencies). Domain experts can choose to limit the learning to specific edges (see also Figure 14). To generate DAGs, we used the DAG with NoTears algorithm.

Figure 14: DAG using NoTears Algorithm

Although there are many results that match people’s intuition, there are still many interesting findings in terms of dependencies. Two of the representative findings are about walking and cycling. As shown in Figure 18, the dependency between people’s mean satisfaction score for walking and the connectivity score for walking is negative. Moreover, the correlation between people’s mean satisfaction score for walking and the connectivity score for walking is also weak,

Causal link	Dependencies score	Causal link	Dependencies score
overall walk →	2.26	overall walk →	0.96
overall entertain		overall shopping	
overall car →	1.08	overall car →	2.58
overall walk		overall entertain	
overall car →	1.12	overall cycling →	0.86
overall shopping		overall education	
overall cycling →	2.81	overall cycling →	1.06
overall entertain		overall shopping	
overall pt →	2.95	overall pt →	1.18
overall entertain		overall shopping	
overall business →	1.03	overall business →	1.06
overall walk		overall cycling	
overall business →	-1.05	overall education →	2.38
overall entertain		overall walk	
overall education →	1.31	overall education →	-6.89
overall pt		overall entertain	
overall visit →	0.91		
overall business			
meanPublicSatisfaction →	-4.64	meanPublicSatisfaction →	4.29
overall walk		overall car	
meanPublicSatisfaction →	3.12	meanPublicSatisfaction →	7.36
overall cycling		overall pt	
meanPublicSatisfaction →	2.56	meanPublicSatisfaction →	-2.83
overall business		overall entertain	
meanPublicSatisfaction →	-9.17	meanPublicSatisfaction →	6.35
overall shopping		overall visit	
meanWalkingSatisfaction →	-3.05	meanWalkingSatisfaction →	7.96
overall walk		overall car	
meanWalkingSatisfaction →	-11.65	meanWalkingSatisfaction →	-6.77
overall cycling		overall pt	
meanWalkingSatisfaction →	-1.01	meanWalkingSatisfaction →	-4.69
overall business		overall education	
meanWalkingSatisfaction →	5.01	meanCyclingSatisfaction →	-1.13
overall visit		overall walk	
meanCyclingSatisfaction →	2.93	meanCyclingSatisfaction →	-3.64
overall car		overall cycling	
meanCyclingSatisfaction →	-2.78	meanCyclingSatisfaction →	0.81
overall business		overall entertain	
meanCyclingSatisfaction →	1.05	meanCyclingSatisfaction →	1.21
overall visit		meanPublicSatisfaction	
meanRoadSat →	6.26	meanRoadSat →	9.49
overall walk		overall car	
meanRoadSat →	1.35	meanRoadSat →	-1.98
overall cycling		overall pt	
meanRoadSat →	-3.19	meanRoadSat →	1.48
overall business		overall education	
meanRoadSat →	0.86	meanRoadSat →	5.83
overall entertain		overall shopping	
meanRoadSat →	-5.62	meanRoadSat →	0.89
overall visit		meanWalkingSatisfaction	

Table 3: Dependencies scores learned from merged data on Connectivity scores and satisfaction rates.

Figure 15: Heat map depicting correlation between the connectivity scores by mode of transport, reason for transport, and mean satisfaction scores for different modes of transport.

	overall_walk	overall_car	overall_cycling	\
overall_walk	1.000000	0.713244	0.900865	
overall_car	0.713244	1.000000	0.847123	
overall_cycling	0.900865	0.847123	1.000000	
overall_pt	0.917933	0.735624	0.902316	
overall_business	0.888617	0.851393	0.929737	
overall_education	0.957812	0.825696	0.964707	
overall_entertain	0.854495	0.735407	0.882950	
overall_shopping	0.887918	0.785347	0.893375	
overall_visit	0.887798	0.837920	0.926942	
meanPublicSatisfaction	0.359822	0.437943	0.427842	
meanWalkingSatisfaction	0.102378	0.144052	0.117321	
meanCyclingSatisfaction	0.003574	0.002146	-0.013780	
meanRoadSat	0.239671	0.332324	0.286954	

Figure 16: Correlation coefficients for the connectivity scores by mode of transport, reason for transport, and mean satisfaction scores for different modes of transport.

Figure 17: Mean public transport satisfaction

Figure 18: Mean walking satisfaction

Figure 19: Mean road satisfaction

Figure 20: Mean cycling satisfaction

which is shown in Figures 15 and 16. The same dependency (strong negative dependency) can be observed for cycling as well, see Figure 20, also, in the correlation heat map in Figure 15. The other modes showed logical dependencies with positive dependency scores between satisfaction and connectivity scores.

To note, correlation is not causation and dependencies scores may be more meaningful than correlations. Multiple algorithms for DAGs learning can be tested in the future to produce a graph representation, such as a Causal Bayesian networks. Following this, multiple scenarios can be tested to improve decision-making.

As a result of our research, we believe the possible reason for this counter-intuitive conclusion is the influence of external factors. The fact that the connectivity scores for walking and cycling are high does not mean people's scores for satisfaction will be high. The climate, the environment, and even the sense of security can all affect people's experience. They are particularly important as cycling and walking are the modes of travel that receive the most significant influence from the outside environment compared to driving and using public transport. However, only physical proximity is taken into account when calculating connectivity scores.

Another difficulty we encountered in our research process is that the satisfaction data itself is region-based. As a result, the satisfaction data for all LSOAs in a certain region are the same. Although the number of samples (30415) we have after data cleaning is close to the number of LSOAs, the satisfaction data we have does not have such a high level of resolution. This also prevented us from getting more detailed results.

3.2 Recommendations

We have two recommendations for the subsequent data collection. Firstly, we believe that external factors should be taken into account when collecting connectivity scores, and domain experts should be involved in this stage. Secondly, we suggest that satisfaction data collection should be broken down to the LSOA level instead of the regional level.

4 Mobile Data 1: Aggregate Analysis and modelling

4.1 The trajectory of the travelling population

To further understand how people travel over time on different days, specifically the growth of the travelling population on weekdays, weekends, and holidays, we use data collected from mobile phones. This data captures people's travelling activities at different times of the day in different areas (Mobile data 1).

This data set includes information about where trips are going from and to, as well as the time of day. It also contains variables that record people's spending power and travelling purpose. The data was collected before the Covid-19 pandemic.

4.1.1 Overall travelling growth

Our first objective is to understand the overall growth of the travelling population in the UK. Since people's travelling patterns vary across different days, we randomly selected three distinct days from weekdays, weekends, and national holidays in the data set.

The three diagrams in Figure 21 depict the trajectory of the overall travelling population growth on the different days, averaged by different areas across the UK. All three diagrams suggest a non-linear growth of the travelling population from 5:00 to 24:00.

On a weekday, the travelling population climbs to its first peak around 10:00 and then reaches a second peak around 16:00. During the day on a weekend, the travelling population growth follows a bell shape, and after reaching the highest level after midday, it slowly decreases until 22:00.

On a national holiday, such as Christmas Day, the travelling population mainly increases in the morning, but slightly slower compared to a weekday or the weekend. The significant decrease in the travelling population is found after midday and in the evening. Interestingly, we found another increase in the travelling population around midnight on both the holiday and the weekend.

(a) Weekday

(b) Weekend

(c) Holiday

Figure 21: Overall travelling growth

4.1.2 Modelling travelling growth

To provide statistical insight into the travelling population growth, we performed a regression analysis (Figure 22). As the travelling data is often compiled in time series format, we applied the growth modelling approach by using the time (i.e. hours) as our independent variable, and the travelling population as our dependent variable. We used the weekday subset data to perform this modelling.

Results (DV: Travelling population / weekday)		
	M1	M2
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>Estimates</i>
Time (hour)	-10.507 *** (0.748)	180.761 *** (4.266)
<i>Time(hour)</i> ²		- 6.595 *** (0.144)
Area fixed effects	Yes	Yes
R square	0.757	0.761
Observations	187400	187400

Notes: Standard errors in parentheses.
 * $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$

Figure 22: Regression analysis results of travelling population growth.

Our models provide the statistical evidence of travelling population growth. To control for factors that vary across different areas, Model 1 (M1) used the fixed-effects estimator, suggesting that the travelling population decreases by around 11 people per hour during the weekday, on average per area. As our previous diagrams highlight a non-linear growth of the travelling population, we added a non-linear function in Model 2 (M2), along with area fixed effects. Results of Model 2 suggest a concave growth of the travelling population. We calculated the predicted values of our models and plotted them in the diagram in Figure 23.

4.1.3 Travelling population and spending power

The diagrams in Figure 24 depict the trajectory of travelling population from 05:00 to 24:00 on a randomly selected weekday, weekend and a national holiday (i.e. Christmas) based on the total population in different categories of their spending power.

There is a sharp increase in the travelling population across all spending power groups in the early morning. The travelling population decreases between 09:00

Figure 23: Regression Models 1 and 2 predicted values against time.

to 12:00. However, a continuous increase in the travelling population is captured from the highest spend power group until 18:00.

On the weekend and holiday, the travelling population is also seen to increase in the morning. While the growth of the travelling population continuously holds constant between 11:00 to 14:00 for people in lower spending power groups, the highest spending power population seems to travel less after midday. Interestingly, a growth in the travelling population is noted in the late evening, starting from 22:00.

Similarly to the weekend, travelling population growth shows a similar trajectory in the holiday. However, after the middle of the day, the travelling population still sees a constant growth in the afternoon and early evening, which is different from the weekday and weekend. A peak of the travelling population is captured around 19:00.

In summary, the trajectory of the travelling population is similar across different spending power groups during the morning period. The population with the highest spending power make continuous travels during the day. However, on a holiday, a discontinuous travelling growth is shown at multiple periods of a day across different spend power groups

(a) Weekday

(b) Weekend

(c) Holiday

Figure 24: Travelling population and spending power

4.1.4 Travelling population and trip purposes

We also analysed how different purposes for travelling drive the growth of the travelling population (Figure 25). On the weekday and the weekend in our sample, with the decrease in resident trips, a greater proportion of the population travels for work and visits. As for visiting travellers, they are likely to stay at their first destination between 12:00 to 21:00, followed by a second trip at night.

On a national holiday, there is a significant decrease in people travelling for work compared to the weekday and the weekend. The majority of the population travels for visiting on the national holiday. Despite the visiting population reaching the peak at 15:00, we don't see a second increase in visitors' travelling for the rest of the day.

4.1.5 Implication and insights for future analysis

Based on the analysis of the travelling population on different days, we provide the following recommendations. First, while transport services mainly focus on rush hours on weekdays, the travelling population also sees a significant increase during specific hours of weekends and holidays. Hence, transport service providers should also pay attention to these unconventional rush hours. Second, people with lower spending power are likely to travel late at night (i.e. after 21:00) across all three types of days. In order to provide better transport access for this population group, sufficient services should be considered during this time of day. Third, although travelling population growth varied across different spending power groups and travel purposes, a bell-shaped trajectory captures the overall travel growth in a day, which is consistent with our empirical model.

Building on the data that captures the volumes of people travelling on different days, along with the information about people's spending power and travel purposes, we found that the total population is not constant across different hours of the day, after adding up from all areas. Specifically, the population increases to its highest level around midday. Hence, we assume that the mobile applications (data collectors) only focus on the travelling population, without accounting for the general population in different areas. Although we normalised the data in our analysis, future work should standardise the data based on its original population at each area (MSOA), particularly before merging with different data sets.

(a) Weekday

(b) Weekend

(c) Holiday

Figure 25: Travelling population and trip purposes

4.2 Travellers' Attributes

In this section we are interested in understanding travel users' attributes from Mobile Phone data 1.

4.2.1 Data Description

Mobile phone data 1 dataset ranges from 01/03/2019 to 29/02/2020. In order to compare the travellers attributes, the process below compares the data between 03/01/2019 and 21/02/2020, as both these days are Fridays.

The description of traveller attributes, from aggregate mobile phone data 1, the variables are departure time, MSOA, age, gender, spending power, travel purpose, people count. The departure time and people count are numeric, the age, gender, spending power, travel purpose are categorical variables. For MSOA, we aim to merge this geographical information with real region (like South East, London), find these variables varies by geographical region.

4.2.2 Preliminary Data Processing

The preliminary data processing including three steps: 1. merging the MSOA data with real region data; 2. remove all of the missing values; 3. convert all categorical variables into numerical variables. For gender, 1 represents female, and 2 represents male. For age, group 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 represent the age 18-24, 25-34, 35-44, 45-54, 55-64, 65+ respectively. For spending power, group 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 represents the spending power 0-19, 20-39, 40-59, 60-80, 80-99 respectively.

4.2.3 Description of Travellers' Pattern

Figures 26 and 27 provide us with departure times. We find that the number of travellers is less in 2019. We find no travel departures between 1am 4am, and most of the trips take place between 9am and 5pm.

According to the distribution of travellers by purpose (Figures 28 and 29), we find that most of the travellers are resident. In 2020 we find that there are more visitors.

The distribution of travellers by region shows that travellers in London and the South East travelled more frequently, while Wales and the North West travelled

Figure 26: Distribution of Departure time 2019

Figure 27: Distribution of Departure time 2020

Figure 28: Distribution of Traveller by Purpose 2019

Figure 29: Distribution of Traveller by Purpose 2020

least frequently (Figures 30 and 31). This pattern is both true from 2019 to 2020.

Figure 30: Distribution of Traveller by Region 2019

The distribution of travellers by spending power shows that the travel numbers are falling slightly with rising spending power (Figures 32 and 33).

As London include a large number of travellers, we extracted travel time information for London and found that there is a distinct peak time in London, between 8am and 6pm. Also, the difference between the highest peak and lower frequency time period data is 1 million (Figures 34 and 35).

4.2.4 Factors Affecting Travel

We further explored factors that can affect number of travellers such as age, gender, and spending power. Because the data-set count by age and gender and spending power separately. We built a regression model for age and gender factors and a separate one for spending power. Regression results for the effects of age and gender are in Figure 4. We find that females contribute significantly more to the number of trips than males. We also find that the largest contributors to travel numbers are those aged 24-45.

The contribution of spending power to the number of trips can be found in Figure 5. We find that the contribution of all groups to trips is negative.

Figure 31: Distribution of Traveller by Region 2020

Figure 32: Distribution of Spending Power 2019

Figure 33: Distribution of Spending Power 2020

Figure 34: Distribution of Traveller Departure Time in London 2019

Figure 35: Distribution of Traveller Departure Time in London 2020

	Estimate	Standard Error
Intercept	41.9***	0.11
Age 2	35.8***	0.15
Age 3	36.9***	0.15
Age 4	37.9***	0.15
Age 5	18.4***	0.15
Age 6	13.6***	0.15
Male	-6.7***	0.08
R^2	0.02	

* $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$

Table 4: Regression Result by Age and Gender. Age is discretised in 6 groups.

	Estimate	Standard Error
Intercept	376.4***	0.8
20-39	-5.1***	1.1
40-59	-6.8***	1.1
60-80	-8.1***	1.1
80-99	-7.1***	1.1
R^2	0.00003	

* $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$

Table 5: Regression Result by Spending Power.

5 Mobile Data 2: Individual Journeys Analysis

The primary aim of this analysis was to assess the insights about travel patterns that could be gained from the BetterPoints user app data (Mobile phone data 2). This section details our exploratory data analysis and cautions against relying solely on this dataset for representative insights.

5.1 Dataset description

5.1.1 Data source

The source of the data is The BetterPoints App. The app aims to encourage, reward and measure behaviour change including increasing movement and physical activity for better health and climate. The website describes the app as an incentive to “shift transport mode at scale”.

The app uses a mix of gamification, tracking and rewards (vouchers) to help users meet a number of challenges over 3-36 months. The app is free to use and has been downloaded over 50,000 times.

5.1.2 Data description

The subset of data used in this analysis is limited to

- 2 months: April and November 2019
- 121 UK postcode areas (out of the 124 postcode areas covering the whole of the UK)

- 7045 unique app users

The information collected by the app is described in Table 6:

Variable name	Data type and example instances
Unique ID	alphanumeric
Mode	walk/bus/car/cycle/train
StartTime	Datetime in April/Nov 2019
EndTime	Datetime in April/Nov 2019
Postcode Area	e.g. M, LE, SM, WA

Table 6: Variables names and their data type and example instances in Mobile data 2.

5.1.3 Nomenclature

To avoid confusion, the following definitions apply to the rest of the analysis:

- A **Trip** is a single unit of travel that the app user took with a single mode of transport. It should be equivalent to a single row in a data table.
- A **Journey** is a sequence of trips that were undertaken by the app user. For example, one journey might consist of a walk to the bus stop, a trip by bus to the train station, a trip by train, and a walk to the office.

5.2 Defining a journey

5.2.1 Defining waiting times

In defining a journey we first calculated the duration between trips taken by the same app user within a 24-hour period (between midnight and 11:59pm). This excludes trips that took place in the night (for example, app users coming home late with their journey starting at 11pm and ending at 1:30am), but we have found that these journeys are not that common and such an approach simplifies greatly further analysis.

5.2.2 Numerical constraints of a journey

A single journey may consist of multiple trips. The trips might have some reasonable waiting time in between them, while still being a part of the same

journey. This cut-off time was initially estimated to be 45 minutes and as seen in Figure 36 it was a reasonable choice because it captures most of the trips for bus, cycle, train and walking. Only for cars, the distribution of waiting times is significantly flatter and it would be very difficult to provide one cut-off time that clearly separates journeys with longer waiting times in between trips from separate journeys.

Figure 36: Histogram of wait time since a previous trip across different modes of transport

5.3 Peak travel times

We created a flag for journeys that took place wholly or in part during peak travel times. Peak travel times were defined according to the TFL criteria as 06:30-09:30 and 16:00-19:00 on Monday and Friday, excluding public UK holidays . We counted the long Easter weekend (19-22 April 2019) as a public holiday.

5.4 Data quality issues

5.4.1 Analytical findings

Initial analysis of the data showed that there are many data points that are questionable in terms of their adequacy for further analysis.

Data Issue	Example	Solution
Overlapping trip times	A new trip has started before the previous one was finished	Merging into one trip (see Figure 37)
Too long trips	Walking trips that last for 14 hours or multiple days	Marking as an outlier and removing
Too short trips	Trips less than one minute long	Marking as an outlier and removing
Multiple short trips within one journey	A couple of consecutive short trips of the same transport mode with a very short waiting time between them	Merging into one trip under the assumption that the wait time between has to be not longer than 5 minutes (see Figure 37)

Table 7: Analytical findings

Major identified types of outliers are described in Table 7.

JourneyMode	StartTime	EndTime	Duration
Walk	2019-04-01 03:37:52	2019-04-01 20:24:57	16H 47M
Walk	2019-04-01 09:55:58	2019-04-02 08:27:16	22H 31M
Walk	2019-04-02 15:42:15	2019-04-02 15:42:18	3S

Table 8: Data examples with excessively long or short trip duration

For this reason, the data had to be reduced, to contain only entries that will provide reliable information on the underlying patterns. The summary of such cleaning process is depicted in the schema 38.

Figure 37: Processing Individual Trips

Figure 38: Process for Cleaning Data

5.4.2 Comparison to the user experience

We have found that the above findings are consistent with what the app users are experiencing. The app has 256 reviews with an average rating of 3.5 on the iOS Apple store and 1198 reviews with an average rating of 2.6 on the Android store. Some of the the problems encountered are pointed out in Figure 39, together with corresponding reviews.

(a) Not recording journeys

(b) Dropping the journey before it's ended

(c) Recording wrong transport mode, recording wrong times of journeys

(d) Large battery consumption

Figure 39: Technical issues described by users of the app in the reviews

They align with our analytical findings. It is worth pointing out that excessive battery consumption by the app might be a source of the wrong records too—if the phone runs out of battery, but the journey is not marked as finished until the

user recharges their phone many hours after.

5.5 Findings

5.5.1 Information that can be extracted from the data

After the initial cleanup of the data, the analysis was performed on the information extracted with the following findings.

Trip duration Figure 40a shows the distribution of the trip duration for different modes of transport. Clearly, the train trips are the most diverse with most durations being between 10-60 minutes, which aligns with expectations of those trips to be both long and short distance. The bus trips show a tendency to average around medium-length (17-20 minutes), with fewer long-distance trips. The histogram of cycling trips shows something different. The majority of such trips are below 25 minutes and they average around 0-5 minutes. This is understandable because cycling is mostly done for recreational or commute purposes and both of them are limited by personal endurance. This effect would be expected for walking trips, but surprisingly it's not the case - the majority of walking trips registered are of a duration of around 10 minutes. This might be related to the technical issues with an app not registering walks properly.

Day of the week The histograms in Figure 40b show that the number of trips varies throughout the week only for some modes of transport. These are bus, train and cycle. This is an interesting insight because even though public transport trips are expected to be less frequent during the weekend, that is not intuitively the case for cycling. This might show that cycling is primarily used for commuting, which is valuable information that should be considered in planning transport routes in the future.

Hour of the day Histograms presenting the distribution throughout the day (Figure 40c) show a similar tendency. Again, bus, train and cycle show increase during peak times, while car or walking trips don't.

Trip sequences in a journey Figure 41c shows a significant pattern that we observed which is that the majority of the registered journeys do not include public transportation. What that shows is that the majority of the UK population

(a) Distribution of the trip duration

(b) Distribution of trips across days of the week

(c) Distribution of trips across the hours of the day

Figure 40: Trip duration distributions

(a) Histogram of the average daily trips per app user

(b) Histogram of the average daily journeys per app user

(c) Distribution of journey sequences

Figure 41: Daily trips, journeys, and journey sequences.

still relies on their own means of transport (walking, car, cycling). It is known that such creates limitations for underrepresented groups (people with lower income, disabilities or health issues) who might not be able to use or afford a car to commute to work, school or healthcare centres.

Journeys/Trips per day Figures 41a and 41b show histograms of average daily trips and journeys, respectively. We have measured the median to be 2.3 for journeys and 3.8 for trips. We can see in the charts that there is a clear peak of around 2.5 for journeys and 4 for trips. That means that the majority of users are having around 4 trips per day which form 2.5 journeys per day. That aligns with the expectation that most people move around twice a day (to and from work) with some extra trips for grocery shopping or entertainment. It makes sense that there are 4 trips and 2 journeys—the journeys having 2 trips each (for example, driving the car and walking from parking, walking to the bus and commuting by bus etc.).

5.5.2 Representativeness

According to our judgement, people who download the app are likely not a good representation of the UK population. We have identified the following major incentives to download and use the such app:

- Willingness to improve one's health
- Willingness to lead a more sustainable lifestyle
- Willingness to receive the benefits from the app (vouchers)

These are likely to introduce a strong bias on the underlying patterns because they will apply to a very specific subset of people. That makes a behavioural analysis of such data unreliable.

5.5.3 Generalisability of the App Users to the Wider Population

While there is broad coverage across the UK, each geographical region has a small number of app users. Figure 42 shows the number app users residing in each of the postcode areas. 59 of the 121 postcode areas have less than 20 app users. Because of the small sample size and lack of demographic information, it is not clear how representative the app users are of the general population in their respective areas.

This means that individual journey patterns can not be generalised to the wider population in each geography.

Figure 42: Bar Chart

5.5.4 Attrition rate

While the total number of unique users increased from April (N = 3495) to November (N = 5199), the rate of attrition was high. 53% of April users (N = 1846) did not use the app in November.

A key aim of the BetterPoints app is to incentivise increased use of walking and public transport in the medium and long term. However, the high rate of attrition is a major methodological limitation. Systematic differences between users who continue vs discontinue using the app can distort an analysis of user behaviour change between the April and November datasets.

5.5.5 Waiting Times

We compared the waiting times for trips taken on public transportation at peak and off-peak travel times. The mean waiting time during peak times was 7.52 (SD = 9.44), whereas the mean during off-peak times was 9.10 (SD = 11.02). A Welch two-samples t-test showed that the difference was statistically significant, $t(4035.3) = 5.22, p < 0.001$.

We then compared the waiting times broken down by bus and train trips on each day of the week. Figure 43 shows that the mean waiting times are generally higher at off-peak times and are highest on weekend days. In addition, the mean waiting times for trains are higher than for buses. However, these findings should be interpreted with caution, as the high standard deviation for the waiting times means that the difference is not statistically significant.

Figure 43: Mean Waiting Times

5.5.6 Linear Regression

Multiple linear regression was used to test if the mode of transport and whether the trip took place during peak travel times significantly predicted waiting times.

As waiting times were calculated as the difference between the end and start times of consecutive trips within the same journey, we were only able to analyse waiting times for secondary trips within a journey. If a bus or train ride was the first trip of a journey, it was not possible to calculate the waiting time from the available data. We excluded trips made by walking, cycling or car from this analysis, as choosing a time to start travelling in those contexts is fully within the control of the user, unlike having to wait for public transportation to arrive.

The fitted regression model was:

$$\text{waiting time} = 8.35 + 2.21(\text{train}) - 1.75(\text{peak time}).$$

The overall regression was statistically significant but explained less than 2% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.017$, $F(2, 4708) = 40.94$, $p < .001$). We found that both train trips ($\beta = 2.21$, $p < .001$) and peak travel times ($\beta = -1.75$, $p < .001$) significantly predicted waiting times.

Given that the regression explained so little of the variance, we visualised the waiting times for bus and train trips at peak and off-peak times. Figure 44 shows that it is difficult to distinguish the waiting times for different kinds of trips.

Figure 44: Peak and Off Peak Waiting Times for Bus and Train Trips

5.6 Conclusions

The BetterPoints user app data captures information that can be used to compute:

- Waiting times for public transportation
- Number and sequence of trip modes used to complete journeys
- Duration of multi-trip journeys

These indicators can be used as a proxy for pain points while using public transportation. It should be noted that long wait times are just one type of pain point. Other pain points that can not be measured from the app data include economic, accessibility and inclusivity issues.

App data can also be used to track changes in travel patterns by

- Mode:
 - Public transport (train and bus)
 - Private car
 - Active travel (walking and cycling)
- Overtime:
 - Weekdays vs. weekends
 - School holidays
 - Seasonally (can be linked to weather information on precipitation and temperature)
- Level of aggregation and disaggregation
 - Overall trends (aggregate information)
 - Differences between groups (car owners, geography)
 - Individual behaviour change

There are a number of caveats to using the data as it currently stands. The lack of representativeness of the app users means that findings cannot be reliably generalised to the whole of the UK. Moreover, the sparseness of data for many postcode areas means that insights cannot be drawn for many geographical areas. Knowing only the postcode area of the app user's home address instead of the postcode areas of the trip starts and ends means it is not possible to infer geographical travel patterns.

Finally, the app data collection is significantly prone to errors as noticed by the app users themselves and apparent in discrepancies in the raw data. Currently, the accuracy of the app in correctly identifying trip modes and times is not reported.

5.7 Recommendations

To address these issues we recommend making the following changes to the app:

- Addressing the battery drain issue. This would help ensure that trips are not recorded for excessively short or long durations while the phone is out of battery. Moreover, improving user experience could potentially decrease user attrition.
- Improving the accuracy of the app tracking through systematically monitoring:
 - How the app’s categorisation of trip mode compares to the ground truth of user categorisation
 - How the app records or does not record the start and end times of trips

Being able to compare the app’s performance to the ground truth would allow machine learning techniques to be deployed to optimise the app’s classification of trip modes and recording of trip times. To obtain the ground truth, the app could undertake user testing in several ways. Select users could manually record their travel behaviours in exchange for vouchers (which are already offered through the app). The app could also flag discrepancies in the data in real time to users by creating push notifications for users to confirm what is happening. For example, if a new trip is initiated 3 seconds after the end of a prior trip using the same trip mode, a user could be asked to confirm it is part of the same trip.

Once these issues with the app have been addressed, stratified random sampling of the UK population could be used to invite people to use the app. There is already a precedent for using sampling in this way to learn about individual travel habits. For example, a selection of respondents to the National Travel Survey (NTS) are asked to complete a 7-day travel diary. In the future, NTS respondents could be asked to complete the 7-day travel diary while using the app simultaneously. This approach would address bias due to lack of user representativeness and would also offer a ground truth in the form of the travel diary for comparison with the app tracking.

6 Conclusions

In conclusion, the study highlights several key findings regarding transportation patterns and public transport satisfaction. Across all regions except London, the primary mode of commuting is by car. In London, individuals from higher income

bands prefer using the underground, whereas in regions near London, the highest-income households opt for surface rail services. The study also reveals that areas with large cities are highly connected, while neighbouring rural areas have lower connectivity scores. Surprisingly, there is a negative correlation between public transport satisfaction and connectivity scores for walking and cycling, possibly influenced by external factors such as weather and safety. Additionally, the data indicates that people under 45 years old account for the majority of trips, and off-peak times involve longer waiting periods between trips.

Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed. Firstly, merging different datasets to analyse geographical distributions of single and multi-stage trips could provide valuable insights. Secondly, the adoption of standardised geographical area categories for analyses across different time frames would be beneficial. To better understand the relationship between connectivity scores and other datasets, it is suggested to include external factors such as weather, environmental conditions, and safety in the calculation of connectivity scores. Lastly, improving the quality of mobile phone data is essential by addressing issues like phone battery drain, the accuracy of app tracking for mode of transport categorisation, and the precise recording of start and end times.

Overall, these conclusions and recommendations offer valuable guidance for future research and policy-making in the transportation sector.

7 Team members

Aditi Dutta is a PhD candidate at the University of Exeter (Q-Step), studying online misogyny. She contributed to linking the NTS (Stage and Trip) dataset to the connectivity scores EW, alongside performing initial exploratory data analysis and data wrangling for both. She also contributed to writing up the section dedicated to that part of the report.

Arun Frey is a postdoctoral research scientist at the Leverhulme Centre for Demographic Science. He contributed to the Mobile Phone - Individual Journeys Analysis. He performed data wrangling and exploratory data analysis on the mobile phone data and created the descriptive data visualisations in this section of the report.

Lara Johnson is a PhD student in the School of Informatics at the University of Edinburgh. She contributed to the Mobile Phone - Individual Journeys Analysis. She performed data wrangling on the mobile phone data; analysed the app user experience, user attrition rate and waiting times; created the diagrams and some of the data visualisations; and wrote the conclusions and recommendations sections of the report.

Shubham Joshi is a Data Scientist in Shell Research Ltd. He contributed to the NTS - Individuals and Households datasets. He linked both datasets and conducted data preprocessing, plotted exploratory plots of geographical distribution of mode of transportation by demographic and economic indicators.

Eya Meddeb is a PhD student at the University of Worcester working on predicting employee turnover using causal inference and machine learning. She contributed to merging the NTS attitude (satisfaction metrics) and Connectivity scores using a DAG learning algorithm named Notears.

Zuzanna Onderko is an MSc student at King's College London studying Complex Systems Modelling. She contributed to the Mobile Phone - Individual Journeys Analysis. She worked on data wrangling and defining waiting times and journeys. She did exploratory data analysis and wrote data description, journey definition, data quality issues and findings sections of the report.

Binur Orazumbekova is a PhD student at Queen Mary University of London studying in 'Health Data in Practice' program. She contributed to the NTS - Individuals and Households datasets. She performed data preprocessing, conducted exploratory analysis of geographical distribution of mode of

transportation and contributed to writing the corresponding section in the report.

Ozioma Paul is a PhD student at the Alliance Manchester Business School. She contributed as one of the facilitators for the challenge as well, organising the group as well as the presentation output. She also worked on exploratory data analysis for the NTS dataset.

Weizhao Su is a PhD student at the University of Southampton in Operational Research for Traffic Allocation and Congestion. She contributed to the Travellers Attribute. She processed Mobile data 1, people counts in age and gender and spending power. She processed the preliminary data and merged it into a useful dataset. For analysis of the data, she used the regression model and find indicators that influenced the number of people travelling, and plotted some graphs.

Ye Wei is a PhD student in the department of computer science at Loughborough University. He contributed to the analysis of connectivity scores EW and NTS attitude. He participated in the pre-processing of the connectivity data, including clustering them based on regions. He also applied some regressions methods to validate the results in this part.

Skyler Xie is a PhD student and the founder of Quantitative Solutions at the University of Warwick. He contributed to the mobile data - travelling population growth analysis. He performed data processing, modelling experiment, visualisations and report writing. He was also a facilitator of this project, monitoring the progress of this challenge along with Ozioma, Marko (PI) and DSG Team.

Other contributors: Kejian Qian and Zhongtian Sun.

Marko Tešić is a Royal Academy of Engineering UK IC Postdoctoral Research Fellow at Birkbeck, University of London. He was a Principal Investigator for this challenge. His contributions include: scoping a data science challenge in collaboration with the data provider, the Department for Transport; supporting the DSG participants during the challenge week; and finalising the final report on the outcomes of the challenge.

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Appendix

The code used to calculate weighted average of connectivity and mean connectivity for every county.

```

1 # Function for finding weighted average
2
3 def weighted_average(df, values, weights):
4     return np.round((sum(df[weights] * df[values]) / df[weights].
5         sum()), 2)
6
7 # With respect to population
8 # This is with just one of the examples. Similar code used for the
9     other variables with combinations of purpose and mode
10 # Business_car
11 df_connectivity_1_Business_car = df_connectivity_1.groupby('lsoa').
12     apply(weighted_average, 'Business_car', 'Population').to_dict()
13 df_connectivity_1['Business_car'] = df_connectivity_1['lsoa'].map(
14     df_connectivity_1_Business_car)
15 # Shopping_car
16 df_connectivity_1_Shopping_car = df_connectivity_1.groupby('lsoa').
17     apply(weighted_average, 'Shopping_car', 'Population').to_dict()
18 df_connectivity_1['Shopping_car'] = df_connectivity_1['lsoa'].map(
19     df_connectivity_1_Shopping_car)

```

Listing 1: Weighted average of connectivity across different combinations of purpose and modes on LSOA level

Figure 45

```

1 # Taking the mean for each county
2
3 df_connectivity_1 = df_connectivity_1.groupby('County')['
4     Education_car', 'Business_car', 'Shopping_car',
5     'Education_walk', 'Business_pt', 'Education_pt',
6     'Visit friends at private home_car', 'Entertain / public
7     activity_car',
8     'Business_walk', 'Shopping_walk', 'Business_cycling',
9     'Education_cycling', 'Shopping_pt', 'Entertain / public
10    activity_pt',
11    'Visit friends at private home_pt', 'Shopping_cycling',
12    'Entertain / public activity_walk',
13    'Visit friends at private home_walk',
14    'Entertain / public activity_cycling',
15    'Visit friends at private home_cycling'].mean().round(
16    decimals = 2)

```

Listing 2: Mean connectivity across every county

Figure 46

```

1 # Create a column for the scores
2 df_NTS_trip_stage['connectivity_score_Dest'] = ''
3 df_NTS_trip_stage['connectivity_score_Orig'] = ''
4 # NOTE: nan values here correspond to counties which do not match
5 # Also, this code only shows for the first two.
6 # It is similarly used for the other categories in the new variable
   'purpose_mode'
7 for each in df_NTS_trip_stage['purpose_mode']:
8     if each == 'Business_car':
9         df_NTS_trip_stage['connectivity_score_Dest'] =
df_NTS_trip_stage['TripDestCounty_B01ID'].map(
dict_connectivity_Business_car)
10        df_NTS_trip_stage['connectivity_score_Orig'] =
df_NTS_trip_stage['TripOrigCounty_B01ID'].map(
dict_connectivity_Business_car)
11    elif each == 'Shopping_car':
12        df_NTS_trip_stage['connectivity_score_Dest'] =
df_NTS_trip_stage['TripDestCounty_B01ID'].map(
dict_connectivity_Shopping_car)
13        df_NTS_trip_stage['connectivity_score_Orig'] =
df_NTS_trip_stage['TripOrigCounty_B01ID'].map(
dict_connectivity_Shopping_car)

```

Listing 3: Linkage

Figure 47: Code snippet 3

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